

US CGNET FIBER OPTIC REMOTING SYSTEM

C.R. Husbands

R.W. Baskin

Lt. Col. W. Tillman

The MITRE Corporation
Bedford, Massachusetts

The MITRE Corporation
Heidelberg, West Germany

HQ USAREUR
Germany

ABSTRACT

The MITRE Corporation designed and evaluated a highly portable fiber optic remoting system to support the requirements of the U.S. Communications Grid Network (US CGNET) program in Europe. This proof-of-concept system was developed to demonstrate the technical and operational feasibility of fiber optics as a replacement for the 26-pair cable assemblies originally selected for connectivity in the US CGNET program. Results of field testing indicate that this developmental fiber optic remoting system meets all US CGNET technical and operational requirements, and significant operational benefit could be derived from deployment of this type of remoting equipment.

INTRODUCTION

The US CGNET is a USAREUR headquarters initiated project designed to augment organic U.S. communications capabilities during exercises, crises, and wartime by subscribing in an organized fashion to the Host Nation Public Telephone System (PSTN). The PSTN, through inherent redundancy, will provide USAREUR headquarters and its major subordinate commands with reliable communications necessary to exercise command and control in support of their combat service and support missions.

The US CGNET concept entails leasing access into the PSTN, at locations where operational requirements may exist, under various contingencies. At each location where connectivity requirements may exist, access into the PSTN is provided by permanently installed distribution boxes. In the Federal Republic of Germany, the PSTN is accessed through AK-701/703 terminal distribution boxes attached to public buildings. The DBP will install and maintain the AK boxes, and "live" circuits will be available to the U.S. military on a full time basis. Access to these boxes will be controlled by USAREUR headquarters.

To physically remote the user operated communications assets from the permanently installed distribution box, USAREUR headquarters commissioned the development of an extension capability. This capability must allow remote interconnection to the public switch network lines some distance from the distribution box. The initial medium chosen for this remoting task was the 26-pair copper cable extensively employed in tactical communication applications. However, this cable is cumbersome, heavy, and highly susceptible to physical damage and electrical upset due to EMI, RFI, and grounding problems.

USAREUR requested that MITRE develop and evaluate a fiber optic replacement for the 26-pair cable. The proof-of-concept fiber optic system, described in this paper, was developed to demonstrate improved capability for the user interfacing with US CGNET. The system will aid USAREUR

in the development of a specification and operational concept for the application of this technology. The use of fiber optic cable as an extension medium for the US CGNET application provides the system with advantages of improved ruggedness, portability, lightweight, and deployment flexibility. Fiber optics is also non-conductive and is available for early deployment (1985-86 time frame).

GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT SYSTEM

In the development of the proof-of-concept fiber optic remoting system, several general specifications on system performance were imposed. The following are the general guidelines used in the development of this system.

The system should be capable of providing remote operation over distances of 1 to 5 kilometers without a repeater.

The system should interface to the Public Switched Telephone Network (PSTN) through AK-701/703 distribution boxes. This interface must be electrically and mechanically compatible with the requirements of the PSTN (the Deutsches Bundespost (DBP) in the Federal Republic of Germany).

The system should be capable of interfacing with a variety of voice-grade terminal devices. These devices include commercial telephone units, facsimile machines, and data modems. Demonstration systems must also be capable of supporting all remote signaling and supervision requirements.

Primary electrical power for the terminal devices will be acquired from sites at either end of the link.

The system must be compatible with the Federal Republic of Germany's Public Switched Telephone Network, and be approved for use on the network by the Fernmeldetechnisches Zentralamt (FTZ), and the Deutsches Bundespost technical center.

DESCRIPTION OF THE FIBER OPTIC REMOTING SYSTEM

The fiber optic system is intended to provide a remoting capability for interfacing voice grade frequency communications equipment with the U.S. Communications Grid Network. It exploits the advantages of fiber optics to reduce the volume and weight associated with metallic conductor candidates for this application. Furthermore, the fiber optic remoting system allows extension of the deployment range (length) and provides electromagnetic interference (EMI) and radio frequency interference (RFI) immunity.

3.4.1

System Components

The fiber optic remoting system is an optical communications link consisting of two multiplexer units, two fiber optic interface units, associated electrical cabling, and the appropriate interconnecting cabling. Figure 1 shows a

block diagram of the major components of the system and the interfaces between these components. The optical communications link uses light emitting diode (LED) sources and PIN detector/receiver units. The electrical interface supports two-wire operation with direct current (dc) signaling and supervision.

Figure 1. Major Components of the Communication Grid Network Demonstration System

Multiplexer Units

The multiplexer unit in the fiber optic remoting system provides three principal functions: two-wire to four-wire conversion, analog-to-digital signal conversion, and multiplexing of the individually digitized channels into a composite time division multiplexed (TDM) bit stream. In the development of the composite TDM bit stream, the multiplexer must also furnish synchronization to permit proper framing of the data at the receiving end. One of the features required of a multiplexer, for this application, is the ability to interface directly to the German Public Telephone Network (Deutsche Bundespost). To accomplish this task, each of the channel interface cards must match the impedance levels of the telephone network and provide proper signaling and supervision levels. For this task the DX7/28 Few-Channels Multiplexing Equipment, produced by TE-KA-DE, Siemens, and Telefunken for the German Army, was chosen. This seven-channel unit was designed for tactical applications for the German Army, where the operational distance between multiplexers was limited to 50 meters.

The encoding technique implemented in this multiplexer design is digitally controlled delta modulation (DCDM). This is very similar to the continuously variable slope delta modulation (CVSD) technique employed for analog-to-digital (A/D) conversion in U.S. TRI-TAC communication equipments. Although DCDM is a proven technique for voice and facsimile reproduction, some concern was expressed about the ability of this technique to handle high data rate modem information with acceptable error rates under all transmission line conditions. Transmission problems using this encoding technique will probably also occur

if several A/D-D/A links must be cascaded. However, certification of the compatible operation of this device with the DBP Network outweighed these basic concerns in selection of the DX 7/28 as the multiplexer for this application.

The DX 7/28, with its associated shock frame, measures 9.6 inches high by 21.024 inches wide by 14.2 inches deep. The multiplexer weighs 46.2 pounds. For this application, the multiplexer was maintained in its shock frame to reduce potential damage during field testing.

Fiber Optic Interface Unit

The function of the fiber optic interface unit is to interconnect the DX 7/28 multiplexer with a fiber optic cable. In addition to this task, the fiber optic interface unit also provides a patching facility to allow selected end instruments to be interconnected to the multiplexer unit. The fiber optic interface unit was fitted into a mechanical box 5 inches high by 12 inches wide by 9 inches deep. The major components and interconnection between the fiber optic interface unit and the multiplexer unit are shown in figure 2. This diagram illustrates the patching facility between the seven standard eight-pin DBP telephone connectors, mounted on the top panel of the fiber optic interface unit, and the input channel connector on the DX 7/28 multiplexer unit. This interface is normally used on the station subsystem end of the link. The patching facility, associated with the fiber optic interface unit, is shown in figure 3. A parallel connection allows the DX 7/28 to be interfaced directly to the AK 701/703 terminal box at the exchange subsystem end of the link. In the standard German Army deployment of the DX 7/28 multiplexer system, a four-conductor coaxial cable

3.4.2

Figure 2. Major Components of the Fiber Optic Interface Unit

Figure 3. Patching Facility on the Fiber Optic Interface Unit

interconnects the two multiplexers. This configuration limits the separation, for tactical operation, between multiplexers to 50 meters. The information carried between the two multiplexers consists of the input and output data streams and the corresponding transmit and receive clock lines. This information is provided to and from the multiplexers at NATO standard signal levels.

In the fiber optic interface unit, interface logic is provided to convert the multiplexer signal levels from NATO standard to TTL logic level signals, to drive the commercial fiber optic transmit and receive modules. A Manchester encoder in the transmitter module and a Manchester decoder in the receive module allow data and clock signals to be combined for transmission over the fiber optic link. The transmit module employs an LED, to provide the electrical to optical conversion, and is connected to a tactical fiber optic bulkhead connector through a short pigtail and an SMA type 906 connector. The optical receiver module is also equipped with a short pigtail and is interconnected to the tactical fiber optic bulkhead connector through an SMA 906 connector. Both modules are incorporated into a dual in-line type package so they can be easily replaced for maintenance purposes.

Two power supply modules provide electrical power for the components of the fiber optic interface unit. Commercial 220-volt power is provided to the fiber optic interface unit through a standard power cord equipped with a four-prong military connector. This power cord assembly can be removed when the system is being stored or transported.

The power supply modules, level converters, and fiber optic transmit and receive modules can be seen in figure 4. In this photograph, the hinged top panel containing the patching facility has been lifted to expose the major components of the fiber optic interface unit.

Optical Cable Assembly

This system uses a twin fiber optical cable that weighs about 46 pounds per kilometer. The optical waveguide (fiber) is manufactured with a graded-index glass core diameter of 50 micrometers, and a glass cladding diameter of 125 micrometers. The fiber is optimized for performance at a wavelength of 850 nanometers. The fibers are coated with a HYTREL buffer for protection.

The two fibers are incorporated into a ruggedized cable with KEVLAR strength members and a polyethylene jacket.

3.4.3

Figure 4. Major Electronic Components of the Fiber Optic Interface Unit

This cable design is the result of an extensive manufacturing technology program conducted by the U.S. Army CENCOMS, Fort Monmouth, New Jersey. As a result of this program a cable has been developed, for tactical deployment, that will operate under severe environmental conditions and can stand extreme abuse. A similar cable design was tested several years ago at the MITRE Bedford facility, in a roadway test, and successfully withstood 30,000 roll-overs by motor vehicles. The tactical optical cable employed in the demonstration system was provided by U.S. Army CENCOMS from inventory developed under their manufacturing technology program.

Optical cables for the fiber optic remoting system were delivered on 1-kilometer reels. The reels being used in the demonstration system are modified versions of the tactical cable reels designed for the AN/GRC-206 program under development by the U.S. Air Force Logistic Command. Each cable assembly terminates with a two-fiber ruggedized optical connector. Fiber optic connectors on the cable assemblies are compatible with bulkhead connectors on the fiber optic interface units. Connectors employed in this system have been used successfully in a number of tactical fiber optic cable systems now in development or in initial production. All fiber optic connectors have dust covers to protect the fiber ferrules during storage and transportation. The terminated fiber optic cable on the tactical reel weighs about 55 pounds.

SYSTEM TEST OF THE FIBER OPTIC REMOTING SYSTEM

Performance of the fiber optic remoting system for the US CGNET application was evaluated in three phases. The first phase encompassed the initial integration of the components, under local loop conditions, and provided a baseline of performance for the system operating over the DBP Public Switched Telephone Network. In the second phase of

testing, data transmission was attempted over much longer transmission paths. The CRESTED EAGLE 84 field exercise then studied the performance of the prototype fiber optic remoting system while it was passing operational traffic.

Bench Testing

Bench testing of the fiber optic prototype system was conducted at the Area Maintenance Supply Facility (AMSF) at Sullivan Barracks, Mannheim, Federal Republic of Germany, in December 1983. This initial phase of testing was the first attempt to integrate the DX 7/28 multiplexing system and the fiber optic interface units and to test these subsystems through the fiber optical cable assemblies using leased DBP circuits.

As part of this test, frequency response tests were performed on all of the channels of the system in each direction. These tests demonstrated the effects of bandwidth reduction, which results from increased input signal level. This phenomenon is a characteristic of the delta modulation (analog-to-digital) encoding technique used with the DX 7/28 multiplexer. Data showed that the delta modulation slope overload problem may bound the data transmission capability of the fiber optic remoting system. Both wire and fiber optic transmission media were employed in this testing phase. During these system tests, measured data showed no differences in performance between the two transmission media.

Initial Field Testing

The second phase of testing was conducted under field conditions but without going through the AK 701/703 connection boxes. This test series was performed in February 1984 in Heidelberg and Nuremberg, Federal Republic of Germany. The tests were designed to exercise the DX 7/28 multiplexing system and the fiber optic remoting system over operational and simulated DBP common user lines. With the multiplexers connected to the fiber optic interface units, end-to-end link tests were conducted through loop back connections at Nuremberg, and through direct connections to the DBP at Heidelberg. The terminal equipment (telephone, facsimile, and modems) was connected to the fiber optic cable through the German connector blocks in the fiber optic interface units.

The tests indicated that the quality of the DBP voice grade circuits varied significantly from test to test. This variance in quality caused changes of the facsimile transmission speed and impaired the overall performance of the LSI 24/24 data modems. However, the test indicated that in spite of marginal DBP circuits, the fiber optic remoting system performed well.

CRESTED EAGLE 84 Testing

The third phase of testing of the proof-of-concept fiber optic remoting system took place in conjunction with the CRESTED EAGLE 84 field exercise conducted during March 1984.

The first half of the test was conducted at the field location of the 5th Signal Command. The fiber optic remoting system was connected to an AK-703 box and fully deployed by a MITRE/Army team in less than 30 minutes. Figure 5 shows the interconnection of the exchange subsystem hardware to the AK-703 distribution box at the CRESTED EAGLE 84 exercises. The subscriber end was located in the command area of the Headquarters 5th Signal Command. A view of the station subsystem hardware

3.4.4

Figure 5. *Interconnection of the Exchange Subsystem Hardware to the AK 701-703 Distribution Box*

installation is shown in figure 6. Only the DBP telephone and facsimile systems were tested using the fiber optic cable system. Test calls were placed throughout the Federal Republic of Germany. The facsimile attached to the fiber optic remoting system performed very well and, as a result, was used as the prime interconnect system between the 5th Signal Command War Headquarters and other users during the first 2 days of the exercise. Telephones were used with the system for both test and operational traffic with no degradation of voice quality or interruption of transmission.

The system was then moved to the main headquarters of USAREUR. There, the fiber optic remoting system was installed at a remote entry point and terminated at the Office of the Deputy Chief of Staff Operations (ODCSCOPS). Connections were established through existing military distribution boxes that introduced signal distortion into the connecting link. However, the fiber optic portion of the link performed well.

Test Conclusions

The results of this test series established the following facts:

The fiber optic remoting system was lightweight, simple to install, and could be deployed in less than 1 hour per location.

Figure 6. *Station Subsystem Installation*

All equipment tested through the fiber optic system worked well. There was no difference in circuit performance between the fiber optic cable system and the 26-pair copper cable.

The configuration involving separate multiplexer and optic interface units was awkward, each with its own case. In the future both components should be packaged in one case.

The delta modulation technique employed in the DX 7/28 multiplexers for A/D-D/A encoding is unacceptable because of the sensitivity of bandwidth with signal levels associated with this algorithm.

SUMMARY

This paper has reported on the development and evaluation of a Fiber Optic Remoting System for use with the US CGNET. This system was designed to evaluate the technical and operational feasibility of using fiber optics to replace the 26-pair cable originally established as the transmission medium for this application. This evaluation demonstrated that the Fiber Optic Remoting System met all of the technical and operational requirements for the US CGNET application and significant operational benefit could be derived from its deployment.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

It is a pleasure to acknowledge the contribution of S.J. Forde of the MITRE Corporation for his assistance in the design and development of portions of the hardware used in the Fiber Optic Remoting System, and his continued support during the test and evaluation portions of this program.

3.4.5.